

Models And Management Of E-Learning – Case Study At Can Tho University

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 13,2025</p> <p>Accepted: July 14,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : E-learning, Quality Management, Training Management Model, Online Class</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15881203</p>	<p><i>In the context of an integrated and commercial world, the amount of knowledge is continuously multiplied thanks to the profound impact of science and technology as well as the explosion of information technology and competition for development. Many changes are happening, from concept to motto of operation, from the way of thinking and decision making to learning methods. Meanwhile, there exist time and resources limitations to people. To survive and develop, any individual must study regularly and highly adapted to the fluctuations. Therefore, the new society must aim at regularly, lifelong learning in which education should be an open, diversified, flexible, advanced and modern educational system.</i></p> <p><i>In the complicated situation of Covid-19, e-learning has gained attention and became an effective alternative training method to avoid the interruption in the teaching and learning process. The Ministry of Education and Training - the highest education administration agency in Vietnam has also issued documents to direct and allow the employment of e-learning for many tertiary education forms in Vietnam. Following that trend, Can Tho University - a prestigious and long-standing university in the Mekong Delta, has also developed a strategy and proposed an e-learning management model to organize training to meet the needs, ensuring the quality of training, effectively exploiting the strengths of the University.</i></p>

Introduction

Recently, the quality of higher education has been gaining considerable attention globally. Therefore, training models must ensure the quality and comply with quality training models that have been assessed around the world (UNESCO, 2006; Wilger, 1997; Woodhouse, 1999). On that basis, the training management model becomes a tool to ensure and improve the quality of training and reputation of the universities.

In the integration and globalization trend, the openness, diversity and flexibility of education is continuously reflected in the organizational method, in the scope and scale, in the perspectives, the curriculum and in the way of orientating and provoking the learners' thoughts. Advance and modernity are shown in the regular level of updating knowledge in teaching content, training, retraining and improving the qualifications of the teachers, modernization of teaching methods and facilities in the trend of forming global education programs.

Currently, education management models can provide managers of educational institutions with better understandings of the task and its reasons for the management of their courses, departments and institutions. Furthermore, the development and recognition of educational management models in the context of decision making and help to streamline and interpret the actions to be taken. By mirroring these patterns, managers can consider to what extent they may need to reassess and change their management style to improve their organization. The ultimate goal is to help educational institutions manage and ensure the quality of training, especially e-learning.

E-learning has been deployed around the world for a long time, yet there is no official recognition from the state management agency, the Ministry of Education and Training. Therefore, the management of e-learning becomes individual work of each training institution without any common standards to ensure the quality. In addition, given that the Vietnamese education system is divided into many training form, e-learning is considered a training method for distance learning and continuing education. This division aims to differentiate and recognize the value for the full-time training form. This inadvertently underestimates and limits the benefits of e-learning. During the outburst of Covid-19 pandemic, while actively preventing the impact of the epidemic on the country, the government and educational administrators of Vietnam recognized the value and issued the policies in favor of e-learning. E-learning started to gain the recognition from the Ministry of Education and Training - the state management agency for education - as well as the attention from learners and the society. Since then, e-learning gradually became an indispensable part of the national education of Vietnam.

Addressing these aforementioned issues, this article briefly introduces the characteristics, the effectiveness of e-learning, several training management models and propose a model of e-learning management with case study at Can Tho University. Therein, two main methodologies were applied: qualitative analysis using demographic data and quantitative analysis using a 70-item Likert questionnaire distributed to 100 students, 20 lecturers and 12 supporting staffs. The results shall provide an overview of the organization and management of e-learning, describe some management activities at Can Tho University in e-learning and propose an effective e-learning management model. The study also aspires and suggests the demand for further study of the value and effective e-learning management models in the world to apply in the Vietnamese context, especially under the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic these days.

2. Literature Review

The Formal Model (Bush, 2003) or Classical Model (Everard, Morris and Wilson, 2004) is characterised by a high degree of job specialisation and is highly centralised. It has a fixed command structure, rigid hierarchy, top-down communication, firm control, strict procedures and a dogmatic approach (Everard, Morris and Wilson, 2004). Those at the top of the hierarchy have primacy in setting goals, making decisions and formulating policy (Bush, 2003)

The Formal Model has been very influential since the development of theories in educational management (Bush, 2003). With its clearly defined structure and top-down leadership, it is considered to be central to the notion of effective management and many schools and language teaching organisations have adopted, adapted and built on this model to improve efficiency of the management process. While alternative models have been in vogue at various times, the Formal Model remains widespread throughout a range of educational management systems.

However, while many believe that the Collegial Model and other participative approaches 'represent the most appropriate means of managing educational institutions' (Bush, 2003, p.70), others have argued that it is rather idealistic and may lead to a lack of control and direction on the part of management. Therefore, due to its flexible nature, those who attempt to adopt the Collegial Model may fail to implement it fully or effectively for fear of the organisation becoming akin to a rudderless ship.

Whereas the Collegial Model emphasizes mutuality and consensus, the Political Model (Bush, 2003) is built upon the notion that decisions are likely to be made according to the power relationships of the participants. In this model, departments, committees and informal groups promote their own interests and objectives, thus producing an environment in which conflict is the primary characteristic. Such organisations are often dominated by those groups or individuals who are able to promote their own interests above those of their colleagues (Bush, 2003).

The Political Model equates with the Contingency Theory described by Everard, Morris and Wilson (2004) to the extent that, in seeking to secure their own self-interests, departments and individuals focus increasingly in creating a niche and a distinctive identity within the organisation. Over time, this process will result in a culture of conflict, in which the interests of the individual or department take primacy over those of the wider organisation. In this model, the head of the organisation assumes the role of overlord and mediator between managers of various departments. Each manager is heavily involved in bargaining and negotiating in order to ensure effective decision-making. This requires the manager to have a deep understanding of the power relationships within the organisation. If this is to be achieved, a culture of mutual trust and respect must be developed and maintained between the conflicting parties within the organisation.

Advocates of the Cultural Model suggest that the informal norms and rituals which characterise organisations may be equally important as the formal structures when attempting to understand management processes within them (Bush, 2003). In order to have an effective system, managers need to understand and attempt to influence the collective values held by those working in the organisation. This is particularly important for new management who may not be in tune with the culture specific to the organisation in question. By understanding and influencing values so that they become closer to, if not identical with, their own beliefs (Bush, 2003), managers can affect positively the changes they wish to bring about. For effective implementation of change, staff must feel part of the innovation. This requires the manager to utilise the existing culture or develop new attitudes to give staff a sense of partnership in change. Managers are more likely to gain staff support for change by adopting the Cultural Model rather than imposing it via top-down processes, as the Formal Model suggests.

Whilst the models discussed above assume that management of educational organisations is planned and systematic, the Ambiguity Model (Bush, 2003) takes into account the fact that organisations are often faced with unpredictable problems which may not be solved through a rational process. Managers skills in making rational choices depend on whether or not they are able to select an option from a range of alternatives which have been prepared to deal with predictable situations (Bush, 2003). However, in fact, managers are often faced with unforeseen circumstances presented by the internal and external environment for which they are unprepared. These pressures may require decisions to be made which appear to be irrational when seen in the context of an organisation's long-term objectives. It is this 'mix of rational and anarchic processes' (Bush, 2003, p.127) which defines the Ambiguity Model. It is a model which offers little guidance for managers, but one which does help

to explain the sometimes contradictory, ambiguous, and seemingly irrational actions taken by management on occasion.

The Distance Learning Management model meets the demand for university-level human resources (Pham, 2016), according to the above model, it is the management process (CIPO) according to the following elements: Planning of training; Management of the implementation of training planning; Examining, monitoring and evaluating training and finally Management of the impact of context ... In the above model, the management of implementation of training planning is considered the most important step since the education institution and the managers must be able to manage inputs, processes and outputs. The model has practical significance because it can be deployed in higher education institutions. This model manages all stages of the training process, on that basis, the managers can regularly monitor, inspect and supervise the process and also have timely methods of adjusting and handling. The reason arising for the training process always takes place smoothly, avoiding conflicts and errors in training.

3. Methodology

To conduct research that follows decision-making, planning and execution. The research team selected the university's e-learning online classes for a period of three months and applied the quantitative analysis method using the Likert 70-item questionnaire distributed to 100 students and 20 lecturers. The data collected via questionnaires were clearly and reasonably provided by the subjects with the number of 93 students and 17 lecturers. The research content that is relevant and actively serves the research is archived, retained and analyzed for a clear, transparent view of the issues to be solved.

4. Experiments

4.1 Policy of state management agencies

Regarding the governing agency, the Ministry of Education and Training, e-learning was only part of the distance learning modalities (Circular 10/2017/TT-BGDĐT). The training results are not accredited as applicable for full-time training.

However, as of Mar 2021, the Ministry of Education and Training initially recognized e-learning by allowing e-learning to become a part of full-time training (Circular 08/2021/TT- BGDĐT). This is a huge step forward for e-learning. Upon the recognition from the governing agency, e-learning will have the opportunity to be widely deployed. At the same time, there will be a quality management mechanism for e-learning to ensure the quality of training. However, the above policy is in fact still limited to the extent that it grant higher education institutions the possibility to organize e-learning, in particular the teaching and learning should not exceed 30% of the training time or subject, otherwise the learning and training results are not accredited.

4.2 Recognition of the team

4.2.1 The recognition from university management:

The Organization of the Vietnam Association of Universities and Colleges - which represent Vietnamese public and private higher education institutions and colleges in Vietnam for now, has recognized the benefits brought by e-learning within the pandemic period. The organization has consulted with the Ministry of Education and Training on the accreditation of e-learning. Schools in the association also conduct meetings and conferences to share experiences on e-learning management. However, each school still implements its own potential, the individual thoughts of each school and can not be applied to other schools in the association.

4.2.2 Recognition of Can Tho University:

Since 2017, Can Tho University has recognized the advantages of e-learning and developed a pilot project of e-learning for the university's distance learning form. At the same time, the University has invested in facilities for e-learning. During the pandemic, the University has flexibly applied practical experiences in e-learning management for distance learning into formal form of the University and has obtained positive results from the participants.

To obtain an overview of e-learning management at Can Tho University, the research team selected the appropriate criteria in the survey by questioning related subjects from relevant departments as a teacher participating in teaching and students are taking online classes and the results are shown in the table 1:

Table 1. Results of survey of parties participating in e-learning activities

Contents	Target	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Normal	Dissatisfied	Very dissatisfied
E-learning brings more interaction than traditional teaching	Teacher	43.8%	37.5%	18.8%	0%	0%
	Student	42.3%	31.9%	25.8%	0%	0%
Students' learning through e-learning	Teacher	43.8%	31.3%	12.5%	12.5%	0%
	Student	36.8%	49.7%	8%	5.5%	0%
The results of students' learning when applying e-learning	Teacher	37.5%	37.5%	18.8%	6.3%	0%
	Student	34.4%	35%	19.6%	11%	0%

Students' enjoyment of participating in various interactive activities	Teacher	31.3%	37.5%	25%	6.3%	0%
	Student	39.3%	22.1%	23.9%	7.4%	7.4%
Student feedback when participating in activities	Teacher	50%	18.8%	12.5%	12.5%	6.3%
	Student	27%	20.9%	39.3%	6.1%	6.7%
The ability of students to use cognitive activities in e-learning	Teacher	12.5%	31.3%	18.8%	25%	12.5%
	Student	40.5%	37.4%	10.4%	11.7%	0%
Number of students participating in activities through e-learning	Teacher	43.8%	31.3%	6.3%	12.5%	6.3%
	Student	43.6%	19%	8%	10.4%	19%
The basis of evaluation in building teaching methods of e-learning	Teacher	0%	6.3%	18.8%	37.5%	37.5%
	Student	12.9%	20.9%	47.2%	11.7%	7.4%
The school's equipment employed for e-learning lessons	Teacher	43.8%	31.3%	25%	0%	0%
	Student	32.5%	21.5%	25.2%	20.9%	0%
State management agencies' policies support the model of e-learning	Teacher	12.5%	12.5%	37.5%	25%	12.5%
	Student	18.4%	13.5%	68.1%	0%	0%

The above survey results show that those who participated in e-learning have the basic comment that they are satisfied with this training method when the percentage of the content is mostly marked as very satisfied and satisfied. But to look at the strengths and weaknesses, it is necessary to clearly consider the assessed content.

Therein, regarding the lecturers, the content of the student's feedback when participating in e-learning activities is highly appreciated with 50% rated at the highest satisfaction level. The content of this group of subjects with the highest rating of dissatisfaction is the content of the Basis of Assessment in constructing e-learning lessons with 37.5% of the assessment that are very dissatisfied and 37.5% of the assessment of dissatisfaction and no evaluation of very satisfied for this content.

Regarding students, there is a contradiction when the content with the highest rating is very satisfied and the content with the highest rating is very dissatisfied. That is the content Number of students participating in activities through communication. For this content, the very satisfied rating rate is 43.6% and the satisfaction rate is 19%. However, as presented, this content also received the highest student dissatisfaction rating when 19% of students rated it very dissatisfied for this content.

From the survey results, it is possible to observe a positive viewpoint towards e-learning. However, it is also necessary to consider the factors marked as dissatisfaction to improve the e-learning management in order to improve the quality of training. In which, we can clearly see the problem of the management model when there is no consensus on the assessment basis from the state management agency to the university level, so the subjects are still struggling to find the right directions. This requires the construction of an e-learning model by the formal state management agency, the Ministry of Education and Training, to educational institutions which can be applied to all these institutions.

4.3 Teaching methods

The exploitation and application of scientific and technological advances in training by educational institutions has gradually increased its popularity. Especially multimedia technology (Multimedia) as the most interesting technology, it is a 21st-century information technology for management and processing. In the past, computers could only process unipolar which are text, numbers and graphics, causing a feeling of monotonous, rigid, dry, easily boring. Multimedia technology is the general processing of computerized communication patterns, including writings, graphics, images, sounds, etc., which establish a logical link, aggregating into a system. Taking advantage of multimedia technology in the industrial revolution 4.0 with artificial intelligence (AI) to create electronic "folders" will become easier, just one click anywhere on screens can find interesting facts; touching the sky; into the cloud will emerge an airplane: touch the canopy of the tree, a small bird will fly out. Another situation, when watching TV dramas, we can change the drama situation if we do not like it, the actors then perform according to our wishes. Similarly, in the activity of learning to pronounce an English word, if the pronunciation is correct, the computer will encourage us, if we read it incorrectly, the computer will point out, read it correctly and guide learners to correct and pronounce this word according to the standards.

As multimedia technology develops, a new form of teaching is formed - the emergence of multimedia computer teaching systems. It is a form of teaching that teachers will teach through software for online classes or online conferencing, directly exchanging with students. At that time, students will absorb lectures like going to class with a traditional face-to-face form. The questions of the students will be answered by the lecturer

during the class, the lecturers can at the same time check the students' comprehension level through the available features of online software such as: Quick survey, quick quiz, ...

Multimedia technology will help teaching methods to become more vivid, the teaching methods will increase in terms of diversity. Besides, e-conferencing and online classroom software platforms are constantly changing, making virtual classes more and more lively and close to traditional face-to-face classes.

Multimedia technology supports different forms of learning, turning passive absorption of information into active information acquisition, stimulating the creativity of students.

Multimedia computer networks are more convenient for the implementation of distance learning, students in border areas can also hear and see famous scientists in big cities. Multi-media technology has the potential to make classroom-based instruction into home-based instruction and the continuing education could be family-oriented. According to experts' prediction, upon the completion of the information highway, the learning time of students can decrease by 40% compared to before but the acquired knowledge will increase by 30%, the cost will also decrease 30% thanks to the distance learning in a two-way exchange.

In the near future, it can be expected that the scope of using multimedia technology will be more and more expanded thanks to the increasing speed of information and computer engineering. These are the advantages and strong points of e-learning that educational institutions need to pay more attention to exploit.

In addition, the lessons will be recorded and edited so that absent students can track and update knowledge of the lessons that they cannot attend.

A big problem arises, whether there is a loophole or the poor oversight by the school towards learners, this is an issue that the education system and the community in Vietnam are worried about. Therefore, for effective management, the online teaching model will be implemented through a training management system (LMS). Students' learning activities will be managed on the system. Learning activities, task performance, online testing and class participation timing are clearly shown to check the learning progress and manage the quality.

4.4 The trend in taking online classes

In the context of many gaps in funding, programs, documents, infrastructure and advanced legal system that continuing education in the Mekong Delta is facing, distance learning remains its role as a trusted human resource provider for society. Therefore, graduates are expected to be qualified to contribute to the economic and social development of the Mekong Delta region (Duong, 2015; Pham, 2017; Government of Vietnam, 2011). In other words, graduates of distance learning courses should be recognized and effective in society. That does not mean any student with a diploma can fulfill the requirements. Indeed, such students must not only be fully equipped with good theoretical knowledge, but also have good practical skills relevant to their major in order to become effective workers in the future. Above all, professional human resources who can adapt and catch up with international qualifications and progress are expected to be trained by continuing education institutions (Duong, 2015; Government of Vietnam, 2011).

To evaluate the results of continuing education, Griscti and Jacono (2006) and Barriball, While, and Norman (1992) find very little evidence of well-defined tools for measuring the effectiveness or frequency of distance learning. However, some evaluation criteria are given by (Brennan, 1997), Romi and Schmida (2009), and Duong (2015). Key factors include enrollment, completion rates, output performance, accessibility to disadvantaged audiences, cost recovery, student motivation, social acceptance of the program, social benefits and economics for the country (Welsh & Dey, 2002).

To achieve the desired results, distance learning management must always be given priority. Edirisingha (1999) emphasizes that the combination of management input and output and influential factors of management is at the core of the development of data. Rumble (1997) proposes four main issues that influence the implementation of distance learning, as illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Students admitted and enrolled in DL courses at the university (from 2016 to 2018)

Course type	Year	Admitted	Enrolled
Face-to-face	2016	2.577	2.093
	2017	3.415	2.477
	2018	1235	986
Online	2016	966	954
	2017	634	588
	2018	343	300

4.5 E-learning management model

Figure 1. E-learning management model

The proposed e-learning management model is based on distance learning model (Pham, 2016). With the above model, it can be effectively implemented in e-learning management, possibly deployed at Can Tho University. The management of e-learning at Can Tho University will be implemented with 3 specific phases: Development of e-learning planning, management of e-learning activities, testing, monitoring and evaluation of e-learning. These phases are fully and flexibly applied and the process should take into account contextual impacts. The above situation shows that educational institutions only take advantage of the contexts to promptly propose appropriate strategies and decisions to ensure effective implementation of e-learning.

5. Discussion

The trend of employing e-learning has started for many years yet the Ministry of Education and Training of Vietnam still does not have a specific training management model which can be practically applied in teaching nationwide. However, in the complicated situation of Covid-19, the authorities had a different view on e-learning. Accordingly, Circular 08/2021/TT-BGDĐT of the Ministry of Education and Training, taking effects from March 2021, has recognized e-learning as a part of the national education program, has allowed the

employment of e-learning widely to remedy the aftermath of the pandemic, to limit any disruption in teaching and learning while ensuring and improving the quality of training.

Conclusions

Can Tho University has built an e-learning management model for its training activities. With this model, Can Tho University can easily manage e-learning activities. At the same time find out the defects to adjust and improve the model more and more effective. When building the model, the authors also paid attention to the quality of training to ensure and increasingly improve the quality of training through e-learning. In addition, putting e-learning into a template, orientating other schools in the region that apply e-learning can with the management. Gradually bring e-learning to become popular, formal and eligible to widely apply to all forms of training: full-time learning, part-time learning, distance learning, ...

The limitations of this study, the scope of research needs to be broader and deeper involving many subjects in order to have an overview and reliable perspective. In addition, it is also necessary to study the impact on policies and views of educational management agencies and each schools in the work of training management affecting e-learning organization activities.

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